

Design and analysis of modified Kresling origami-inspired deployable solar-energy-powered habitable structures

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Abstract

Origami-based structures with bistable characteristics can be acquired to design habitable engineering systems in rough environments such as space stations and surface bases, which are crucially eager for a stable full-deployed state for serviceability and a stable folded state for launch. This research introduces truncations between layers into typical multi-layer Kresling origami structures to achieve integral bistability of enveloped cylinder structures. This leads to capacity bearing at a full-deployed state without extra locking devices, a necessary feature for habitable structures. A parametric model of the modified structure was developed, allowing for the visualization and optimization of design parameters. Folding and deploying processes were numerically simulated. The bistability of the cylinder structures was confirmed by changes in height during the inflation and deflation processes. The structure's electricity demand is met by flexible photovoltaic modules attached to its surface. A Genetic Algorithm is applied to optimize the structural parameters for maximum photovoltaic production capacity. The findings indicate that this modified Kresling origami structure, combined with flexible photovoltaic modules, holds promise for applications requiring deployable, solar-energy-powered habitable structures.

Keywords: deployable structures, non-rigid origami structures, bistability, parametric model, solar photovoltaic, performance optimization.

1. Introduction

Origami, the ancient art of paper folding originating in China and refined in Japan, has inspired innovative approaches to the design of deployable structures. Origami-based structures can be broadly classified into rigid and non-rigid designs. Rigid origami consists of rigid surfaces connected by hinges (Y. Chen *et al.*[1]) and undergoes minimal deformation during deployment, owing to its non-zero degree of freedom (DOF). In contrast, non-rigid origami structures experience deformation during deployment, often exhibiting geometric nonlinearity and multi-stability(L. Fan *et al.*[2] and P. Bhowad *et al.*[3]).

One of the most extensively studied non-rigid origami structures is the Kresling structure (B. Kresling [4]), which is known for its multi-stability. This structure has shown great promise in a variety of engineering applications, including vibration isolation systems with quasi-zero stiffness (H. Zhou *et al.*[5]), robotic actuators (Z. Tang *et al.*[6]), and pump chambers (H. Shen *et al.*[7]).

This paper introduces a novel multi-layer modified Kresling origami structure for deployable habitats in harsh environments. The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 discusses the properties of the

typical Kresling structure and the novel modifications applied to it. Section 3 covers parametric modeling and visualization of the structure using MATLAB. Section 4 presents a dynamic analysis and deployment tests on a scaled model to study its folding, deployment behavior, and bistability. Section 5 analyzes its photovoltaic production capacity. Finally, Section 6 summarizes the key findings and conclusions.

2. Modification of Typical Kresling Structures

This section presents a new origami-based structure derived from typical Kresling structures. After a brief discussion of the typical Kresling design, the process for deriving the modified structure is outlined. These modifications are critical for achieving the desired bistability, making the structure suitable for applications such as space capsules and rapidly deployable habitats in extreme environments.

2.1. Properties of Typical Single-Layer Kresling Structures

Kresling origami, inspired by the twist buckling of thin-walled cylinders, exhibits multi-stability and unique compression-twist deformation. As shown in Figure 1(a), a single-layer Kresling structure is defined by five parameters: upper edge length a , lower edge length b , equal side length c , diagonal length d , and the number of elements n . These parameters can determine the angle β between the lower edge and the right side of the element. The configuration forms a cone frustum when $a \neq b$, and a cylinder when $a = b$, as illustrated in Figure 1(b).

Figure 1: A single-layer Kresling origami configuration. (a) Crease pattern of a single-layer Kresling origami structure. (b) Single-layer Kresling origami structures. (c) The crease-link equivalent truss model.

The crease-link equivalent truss model provides a simplified illustration of the bistability of a single-layer Kresling origami structure by representing it as a truss composed of a combination of rigid bars and elastic links (T. Yuan *et al.*[8]), as illustrated in Figure 1 (c). The lengths of deformed creases $A_k B_k$ and $A_k B_{k+1}$ are denoted as \tilde{c} and \tilde{d} , respectively. The circumcircle radii of the upper and lower polygons are represented by r and R . To capture the deformation of the elastic links during deployment, the height h of the single layer and the twist angle φ of the upper polygon relative to the lower polygon are introduced to quantify the degree of deployment and folding. Consequently, \tilde{c} and \tilde{d} can be expressed as functions of h and φ , as shown in Eqs.(1). The stability of the structure can be analyzed using the elastic energy function U , as expressed in Eq.(2). k_m and k_v represent the axial stiffness coefficients of the mountain creases $A_i B_i$ and the valley creases $A_i B_{i+1}$, respectively. Based on the theory of elastic stability, the self-equilibrium equations can be derived by setting partial derivatives of U equal to zero, as shown in Eqs.(3).

There can be up to four solutions for the self-equilibrium states, denoted as folded-flat state (h^f, φ^f), unstable state (h^0, φ^0), fully deployed state I (h^I, φ^I) and fully compacted state II (h^{II}, φ^{II}). The stability of each solution is assessed using the Hessian matrix, where a positive definiteness indicates stability (L. Lu *et al.*[9]). The folded-flat state, which neglects panel thickness, is impractical. After assessment, the stable states (h^I, φ^I) and (h^{II}, φ^{II}) are considered as the stable states of the single-layer Kresling origami structure.

$$\begin{cases} \tilde{c}(h, \varphi) = \sqrt{h^2 + r^2 + R^2 - 2rR \cos \varphi} \\ \tilde{d}(h, \varphi) = \sqrt{h^2 + r^2 + R^2 - 2rR \cos \left(\varphi + \frac{2\pi}{n} \right)} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$U(h, \varphi) = \frac{nk_m}{2}(\tilde{c} - c)^2 + \frac{nk_v}{2}(\tilde{d} - d)^2 \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial U}{\partial h} = nk_m(\tilde{c} - c) \frac{\partial \tilde{c}}{\partial h} + nk_v(\tilde{d} - d) \frac{\partial \tilde{d}}{\partial h} = 0 \\ \frac{\partial U}{\partial \varphi} = nk_m(\tilde{c} - c) \frac{\partial \tilde{c}}{\partial \varphi} + nk_v(\tilde{d} - d) \frac{\partial \tilde{d}}{\partial \varphi} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

2.2. Modification of Kresling Origami Structure

In a multi-layer Kresling origami structure, more than two stable states can be observed due to the independence between layers. Multi-stability offers significant advantages in reducing and isolating vibrations in engineering applications (J. Ma *et al* [10] and X. Wang *et al* [11]). However, integral bistability is particularly desirable for an origami-based habitable structure to ensure synchronized deployment and folding of each layer. Therefore, modifications to the typical Kresling structure are necessary to achieve integral bistability in a multi-layer structure.

Truncation factors N_i and M_i are introduced to derive the modified Kresling structures. The lengths of truncated edges are noted as $k_{i+1}^l, l_{i+1}^l, k_i^u$ and l_i^u , as shown in Figure 2(a). For constructing a multi-layer structure, the lengths of truncated edges between adjacent layers must be equal ($k_{i+1}^l = k_i^u$, and $l_{i+1}^l = l_i^u$). Thus, the factor N_i is defined as the upper truncated factor of the i -th layer while the factor M_i is defined as the lower truncated factor of the $(i + 1)$ -th layer. N_i and M_i must satisfy Eqs.(4), where a_i, b_i represent the upper edge length and the lower edge length of the i -th layer, and R_{i1}, R_{i2} represent the circumcircle radii of the upper and lower polygons of the i -th layers.

$$\begin{cases} N_i = \frac{b_i b_{i+1} - a_i a_{i+1}}{a_{i+1}(b_{i+1} - a_i)} = \frac{R_{(i+1)1} R_{i1} - R_{i2} R_{(i+1)2}}{R_{(i+1)2}(R_{(i+1)1} - R_{i2})} \\ M_{i+1} = \frac{b_i b_{i+1} - a_i a_{i+1}}{b_i(b_{i+1} - a_i)} = \frac{R_{(i+1)1} R_{i1} - R_{i2} R_{(i+1)2}}{R_{i1}(R_{(i+1)1} - R_{i2})} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

In addition, the angles between the truncated edges' horizontal projections of adjacent layers must be equal. The angles in the i -th layer are denoted as α_i and β_i , which are illustrated in Figure 2(b). The geometric analysis provides the relationships for α_i and β_i , which are derived from the twist angle φ_i the number of elements n , ensuring that the same φ_i and the same n are necessary for successful assembly of multi-layer structures.

3. Parametric modeling and visualization

Parametric modeling is implemented using MATLAB to facilitate the design and visualization of the Kresling structure. The construction process for deployed stable state I is outlined below, and the same approach applies to stable state II, as the geometry for state II can be defined using the same crease-link equivalent truss model described in Section 2.

Figure 2: Truncation design for a modified Kresling origami structure. (a) The derivation of the modified Kresling origami structure. (b) The relationships between angles.

$$\begin{cases} \alpha_i = \pi - \varphi_i \\ \beta_i = \alpha_i - \frac{2\pi}{n} = \pi - \varphi_i - \frac{2\pi}{n} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

3.1 Generating a Single-Layer Traditional Kresling Structure

Instead of relying on the five parameters outlined in Section 2.1, we employ the number of elements n , the circumcircle radii of the upper and lower polygon R_{i1} and R_{i2} , the height h_i of the single layer, and the twist angle φ_i of the upper polygon relative to the lower polygon for easier construction. These geometric parameters are stored in MATLAB as column vectors: $\overline{A_k B_k}$ ($k = 1, 2, \dots, n$), $\overline{A_k B_{k+1}}$ ($k = 1, 2, \dots, n - 1$) and the location vector of point A_k on the mountain creases. The structure is treated as a basic element for assembling the multi-layer modified Kresling origami structure. Each element is referenced in its own local coordinate system, with the origin positioned at the center of the lower polygon.

$$\mathbf{ArrayM} = \{ \overline{A_k B_k} \}_{3 \times n, k=1 \dots n} \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{ArrayV} = \{ \overline{A_k B_{k+1}} \}_{3 \times n, k=1 \dots n}, \text{ if } k = n, \overline{A_k B_{k+1}} = \overline{A_k B_1} \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbf{LocationA} = \{ \overline{A_k} \}_{3 \times n, k=1 \dots n} \quad (8)$$

3.2 Truncating the Single-Layer Traditional Kresling Structure

Once truncation factors for each layer are defined by Eqs.(4), the intersection points between the truncations and creases are calculated. The point A_{k1} or A_{k2} represent intersections of mountain or valley creases with truncations caused by M_i , while B_{k1} or B_{k2} are similarly defined caused by truncations caused by N_i . After truncation, the crease vectors are updated accordingly. The updated matrices of crease vectors after truncation are as follows:

$$\mathbf{TArrayM} = \left(1 - \frac{1}{M_i} - \frac{1}{N_i} \right) \times \mathbf{ArrayM} \quad (9)$$

$$\mathbf{TArrayV} = \left(1 - \frac{1}{M_i} - \frac{1}{N_i} \right) \times \mathbf{ArrayV} \quad (10)$$

The locations of points A_{k1} , A_{k2} after truncation are updated as follows:

$$\mathbf{LocationA1} = \{ \overline{A_{k1}} \}_{3 \times n, k=1 \dots n} = \mathbf{LocationA} + \frac{1}{M_i} \times \mathbf{ArrayM} \quad (11)$$

$$\mathbf{LocationA2} = \{ \overline{A_{k2}} \}_{3 \times n, k=1 \dots n} = \mathbf{LocationA} + \frac{1}{N_i} \times \mathbf{ArrayV} \quad (12)$$

Similarly, the locations of points B_{k1} , B_{k2} after truncation are calculated:

$$\mathbf{LocationB1} = \{ \overline{B_{k1}} \}_{3 \times n, k=1 \dots n} = \mathbf{LocationA1} + \mathbf{TArrayM} \quad (13)$$

$$\mathbf{LocationB2} = \{ \overline{B_{k2}} \}_{3 \times n, k=1 \dots n} = \mathbf{LocationA2} + \mathbf{TArrayV} \quad (14)$$

3.3 Assembly of the multi-layer modified structure.

The multi-layer modified structure is generated by calculating the node locations for each layer. To assemble the structure, the locations of points B_{k1} and B_{k2} locations from the $(i + 1)$ -th layer are made equal to the locations of A_{k1} and A_{k2} from the i -th layer, respectively. This requires performing rotations and translations for alignment.

Initially, the z-coordinates of A_{k1} and A_{k2} for each layer are set to zero, indicating translation in the element's coordinate system. To align with the global coordinate system of the first layer, rotations are applied to the subsequent layers.

For example, for the second layer, the angle between the vector $\overline{A_{k1}B_{k1}}$ of the first layer and the same vector of the second layer is calculated. A rotation transformation matrix is then applied to ensure the z-direction is consistent. After applying the rotation to matrices $\mathbf{TArrayM}$ and $\mathbf{TArrayV}$, assembly can proceed by ensuring that the locations of B_{k1} and B_{k2} of the $(i + 1)$ -th match the locations of A_{k1} and A_{k2} .

Figure 3 shows a structure with about 1 m high and 0.5 m in diameter. The parametric model in MATLAB is also depicted in Figure 3.

4. Folding-deploying analysis

The Finite Element Method (FEM) and deploying tests on a scaled model are used to analyze the folding-deploying behavior and bistability of the structure.

4.1 Quasi-static numerical analysis

To verify the reliability and bistability, a detailed analysis of the structure shown in Figure 3 is conducted, focusing on its folding and deployment mechanism. This analysis is crucial for controlling the inflation and deflation processes. A dynamic explicit analysis applies uniform pressure to the 3.06 mm thick panels, using PVC material properties for the FEM model. Shell elements are utilized for the FEM analysis, with the elastic modulus set to 1.04×10^3 MPa, Poisson's ratio as 0.39, and density of 1200 kg/m³. The system is considered quasi-static when the ratio of kinetic to internal energy is below 5%. For simulating atmospheric pressure on the structure, 0.877 kPa is represented as 1 simu-atm pressure for the model. The applied pressure during simulation is depicted in Figure 4 with the dot-dashed line.

During the folding and deployment process, snap-through events occur when the applied pressure meets or exceeds the energy barrier. The capsule remains stable without any height variation in stable states I and II, maintaining this stability during 15-20 second and 35-40 second, respectively, without internal pressure. This observation validates its bistability. Despite minor discrepancies in height due to residual strain, the structure performs well under 1 simulated atmosphere of pressure after folding and deployment.

Figure 3: Dimension of the designed configuration.

Figure 4: Model's height and pressure variations with time.

4.2 Scaled model tests

A scale model is made from PVC plates, with creases created using adhesive tape. The model is placed horizontally on a table, with both ends free to move laterally. An air pump is used to inflate and deploy the model, and the deployment process is recorded. While airtightness is not fully guaranteed, the maximum power of the micro-pump is employed to minimize errors due to potential leaks.

The deployment process is shown in Figure 5. A sudden shift occurs when the internal pressure reaches a critical point, demonstrating the "snap-through" effect. Once in a stable state, the model retains its shape even when the pressure drops to zero, confirming its bistability.

Figure 5: Inflation deploying process. (a) Step 1: stable state II (b) Step 2: deploying intermediate state I. (c) Step 3: deploying intermediate state II. (d) Step 4: stable state I. (e) Step 5: state at a certain internal pressure.

This test successfully demonstrates the bistable behavior of the structure, proving that the origami-based design can maintain its deployed configuration without continuous external support. This characteristic makes it suitable for applications such as space capsules and other habitable structures where stability and reliability are paramount.

5. Multi-objective performance optimization design for photovoltaic production capacity

The deployable structure's electricity demand is met by flexible photovoltaic (PV) modules attached to its surface. Based on the structural parameters, this study identifies the following variables for optimization design: the rotation angle φ (rad), the radius of the first layer's circumcircle, R_1 (mm), the radius of the second bottom edge's circumcircle, R_{21} (mm), the radius of the second top edge's circumcircle, R_{22} (mm), the radius of the third bottom edge's circumcircle, R_{31} (mm), and the radius of the third top edge's circumcircle, R_{32} (mm). The optimization design constraints ensure that the deployable configuration satisfies both bistability and the spatial volume requirements for practical use. The optimization performance objectives are maximizing the cumulative total annual radiation (CR) received on the surface and maximizing the ratio of stable state I's height to stable state II's height (Height Ratio, HR). The meteorological conditions of Shanghai, were used for the multi-objective performance optimization calculation of the deployable PV configuration. The optimization was set for 50 generations, with a population of 100 individuals per generation, resulting in a total of 5000 iterations. The Pareto solution set of the 50th generation, which had converged, was selected as the final optimization solution for analysis. The EW-TOPSIS method was then used to select three key design solutions from the optimization results, corresponding to the CR optimal solution, the HR optimal solution, and the comprehensive optimal solution (Figure 6). These optimization solutions reveal the trade-off between the two objectives, CR and HR, and provide valuable references for the design of deployable PV configurations.

Firstly, the results of the single-objective optimization indicate that although maximizing CR and HR can each lead to significant improvements in their respective objectives, there is a trade-off in the performance of the other objective function. For example, when the solution maximizing CR is chosen, a radiation value of 39275000 kWh is achieved, demonstrating that this design can attain a high level of energy efficiency. However, its HR value is 2.16. In contrast, when the solution maximizing HR is chosen, the HR value increases to 2.87, but the CR value decreases to approximately 29145000 kWh. Therefore, to overcome the limitations of the single-objective optimization solutions, this study comprehensively considers both CR and HR objectives and identifies the comprehensive optimal

solution that balances the performance of both. This solution has a CR value of approximately 30802000 kWh and an HR value of 2.27, ensuring a high energy efficiency level while demonstrating a good balance between the two objectives. This optimized solution offers a reasonable trade-off between structural stability and energy efficiency, presenting a more holistic and adaptable design solution.

Figure 6: Optimal solutions under different weights

Moreover, although under certain conditions, the single-objective optimization solutions may better align with practical requirements. For example, in specific application scenarios where either radiation or structural performance has strict requirements, the single-objective solution may provide a more precise answer. However, from a practical application standpoint, the design of deployable PV configurations often needs to consider multiple factors simultaneously, especially the need to balance structural stability and energy efficiency. In such cases, a multi-objective optimization approach can more effectively balance different design goals and improve overall performance, thus offering more rational and feasible design solutions.

6. Conclusion

This study introduces a new multi-layer modified Kresling origami structure for deployable habitats. The modifications ensure bistability, allowing synchronized deployment of each layer. Using MATLAB, we successfully modeled and visualized the structure, offering precise control over its geometry.

Finite Element Method (FEM) simulations confirmed the structure's bistability, while scaled model tests demonstrated its ability to maintain a stable deployed state without external support. This stability is essential for applications in extreme environments.

The multi-objective optimization design of the deployable structure successfully balances energy efficiency and structural stability. The comprehensive optimal solution achieves a cumulative total annual radiation (CR) of 30.8 MWh and a height ratio (HR) of 2.27.

The modified Kresling structure shows great potential for space exploration and the development of deployable habitats and infrastructure. The findings pave the way for further research into origami-based designs for deployable structures in harsh environments.

Acknowledgements

This work has been supported by the Fundamental Research Funds for the Central Universities (CN), No. 2023-2-YB-22.

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